

DRUGS & FINE CHEMICALS

Miles Laboratories announced last week that it raised the price of citric acid by 1c. a pound across the board. The move follows, but does not mirror, an increase by Pfizer announced at the end of the previous week. Pfizer raised i.t.l. prices by 1½c. a pound and t.l. prices by 1c. Pfizer also raised the price of less truckloads and carloads of sodium citrate by ½c. a pound, putting 9,600-pound bags at 33c. a pound and the same tonnage of 275-pound drums at 34c. a pound. Miles, however, did not go along with this increase.

Reportedly, price freeze regulations prevented Miles from instituting all of the changes initiated by Pfizer. Rising material costs and pollution control costs were said to be largely responsible for the increases.

The US market is not the only area to see higher prices for citric just now. A source at Pfizer says that prices in Europe have firmed substantially. Pfizer is gradually bringing a plant on stream at Ringaskiddy, Ireland. The plant has an estimated yearly potential of 50 million pounds (see OPD's Chem Marketing, 8/16/71, page 15).

The source at Pfizer says the plant should be fully on stream in the first part of 1972. The company has no current citric expansions underway in the US, the source said.

Miles is reportedly in the process of expanding its capacity, at Elkhardt, Ind. A spokesman for that company declined last week to comment on the scope of this expansion, but he indicated that earlier trade reports that the company would double its capacity from the current estimated 30 to 50 million pounds a year had been exaggerated.

The firmness in the overseas market may have been partly responsible for the drastic reduction in citric acid imports by the US during 1971. They declined from about a quarter of a million pounds in 1970 to a mere 55,000 pounds in 1971. In fact, they have been falling for years. Ten years ago they totaled about 10 million pounds. The surcharge and rising transportation costs are also blamed for the decline in imports last year.

Export business climbed about 2 million pounds last year, rising from about 7.8 million pounds to about 10 million pounds by the end of December.

Under the new schedule implemented by Pfizer, carloads and truckloads of hydrous were raised 34½c. a pound and anhydrous citric acid to 37c.

In other sectors of the drugs and fine chemicals market, a check of saccharine producers found that sales have slipped in the last few months. A supplier says the fall-off is the result of inventory adjustments.

Ascorbic acid prices are reported still high by trade sources. They say, however, that the comparative softness reported here at the beginning of 1972 continues.

A check of botanicals suppliers found that powdered rhubarb is priced higher than formerly and that one grade of senna leaves has also climbed while a powdered form has dropped as to price since last month.

Ascorbic Acid—A spokesman for a major producer of ascorbic acid said last

THE WEEK'S PRICE CHANGES

Ending April 14, 1972

ADVANCED
Citric acid, bulk, t.l., c.l., 1c. per lb.

REDUCED
Silver cyanide, 80% Ag., 3.3c. per oz.
Silver nitrate, ACS, 2.7c. per oz.

COMPARATIVE PRICE INDEXES

(100=1959 average)

Last Week	Prev. Week	Last Month	Apr. 16, 1971
80.76	80.76	80.72	80.10

For Current Prices See Page 29

week that the market "has softened somewhat" recently.

The spokesman did not say that the decline signalled the passing of a fad (for vitamin C), but that "the effect of Pauling has worn off."

He also said he doubted whether the recent attacks on Nobel Prize winner Dr. Linus Pauling's theories with regard to vitamin C's efficacy have had any effect on consumer demand for the vitamin.

The lowest list quote for ascorbic is now \$4.10 a kilo for 100-kilo lots. Trade sources have said, however, that the general market is above this, and one buyer reported recently that the lowest pricing he had been able to find had the material at \$4.55 a kilo.

In addition, spot stocks of vitamin C continue to be non-existent, or all but non-existent.

Consumers report, and producers largely confirm, that new customers deliveries lag as far ahead as July or August.

So far, there is no statistical evidence as to production of ascorbic this year. Last year, US producers made some 815,000 pounds of ascorbic acid in January. About half as much entered the US market from overseas sources during that month.

This year, imports have been running close to those of 1972. Department of Commerce reports about 974,000 pounds of ascorbic entering the country in January and February combined in 1972. Entries during the same two months in 1971 were about 971,000 pounds.

The big difference is pricing. At the beginning of 1971 import pricing at source was averaging between a third and a half less than the best delivered list prices for domestic material.

This year the price of replacement ascorbic acid at overseas sources is slightly more than the best delivered list price for domestic material (as mentioned before average pricing in the domestic market is above this list price). And this increase does not, of course, include the cost of bringing overseas material into

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Chemical Marketing Reporter
Vol. 201 No. 16 100 Church St., New York, N.Y. 10007
April 17, 1972

Report From Europe
Fiber Joint Investment Plans In Europe Held Jeopardized By Cartel Fines: Anneal To Set

PHS Bypassed on NTA

If the federal government decides to breathe new life into nitrilotriacetic acid, Public Health Service will be playing no part in the detergent builder's resuscitation.

Dr. Jesse L. Steinfeld, Surgeon General of PHS, senses an official policy change toward NTA in the wind, and he is complaining that he and his agency are not even being consulted.

According to an interview with *The New York Times*, Dr. Steinfeld believes the federal government may be about to shift its policy on laundry detergents, allowing limited use of NTA.

Dr. Steinfeld is quoted as saying that he has been "all but eliminated" from a panel to review health hazards

He also charges that technical data from detergent studies that he himself had ordered have been withheld from him by other officials of Department of Health, Education & Welfare, parent agency of PHS.

Dr. Steinfeld's immediate superior in the government hierarchy is Dr. Merlin K. DuVal, Assistant Secretary of HEW, a title that makes him the government's chief health officer.

Dr. DuVal concedes that he has personally intervened to speed up evaluation of NTA's effects on the environment and on safety generally. He had originally asked the National Academy of Sciences to set up a panel to review health hazards

Drug and Fine Chemicals Export: February

Exports of selected bulk drugs and fine chemicals for February, 1972, and comparative figures for January, as reported by the Bureau of Census, are as follows:

	January		February	
	Volume	\$ Value	Volume	\$ Value
Antibiotics				
DHS, streptomycin	17,501,550	432,451	9,229,858	250,233
Erythromycin*	23,748,358	3,688,642	96,970,404	1,621,528
Neomycin*	2,751,667	137,939	3,638,165	150,479
Penicillin	17,209,777	731,474	1,113,036	753,220
Tetramycine*	1,196,005	534,362	1,419,689	320,755
Antibiotics n.e.c.**	20,609,714	5,011,654	20,379,520	6,539,347
Ascorbic acid	30,265	49,771	25,849	55,762
Aspirin	160,338	95,731	183,150	91,078
Citric acid	443,015	143,356	895,526	359,040
Hormones				
Cortisone, ACTH	136	26,848	29	5,756
Hydrocortisone	362	60,997	1,614	211,360
Prednisolone	2,086	1,904,026	1,522	1,136,577
Hormones n.e.c.**	72,481	625,548	92,058	414,326
Sulfonamides	114,157	591,919	92,747	453,280
Vitamins				
Thiamine	9,672	59,623	3,678	21,318
Vitamin A	34,725	151,952	9,097	49,565
Vitamin B ₁₂	9,533	161,947	12,072	121,276
Vitamin B (except B ₂ and B ₁₂)	128,367	253,844	95,303	258,752
Vitamin, n.e.c.**	55,441	253,887	49,661	261,850

* Includes derivatives.
** Not elsewhere classified.
† Million units.

on NTA

so charges that technical
 in detergent studies that he
 had ordered have been with-
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News that West Germany's Federal Cartel Office intends to fine nine
 leading fiber producers a total of DM 49 million (some \$15 million) on
 the grounds that they have operated illegal cartels, has caused conste-
 nation in the industry in Europe. Faced with massive over-capacity, the
 closing of American markets and the inflow of large imports from
 Japan, a number of European pro-
 ducers had been discussing with
 the Common Market Commission in
 Brussels.

By M. C. HYDE
 European Editor

Report From Europe

Fiber Joint Investment Plans

In Europe Held Jeopardized

By Cartel Fines; Appeal Is Set

Vol. 201 No. 16
 100 Church St., New York, N.Y. 10007
Chemical Marketing Reporter
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DRUGS & FINE CHEMICALS

the US and putting it in place at the cus-
 tomer's warehouse.
 The increase reflects the world wide in-
 crease in demand for ascorbic, which out-
 ran substantial increases in production
 of the compound, at least in the US, dur-
 ing 1971.
 During 1970, total production of ascor-
 bic in the US amounted to about 9.8
 million pounds. In 1971, US manufacturers
 made about 11.7 million pounds, US Tariff
 Commission estimates. The increase
 amounts to roughly 19 percent.

Botanicals

A number of botanicals listed in this
 publication will be discontinued with this
 issue, due to reported lack of commercial
 interest. These include:
 Areca nut, balm of gilead bud, buchu
 leaves (extract will be reported), catnip
 leaves, dandelion root, domestic digitalis
 leaves, elm bark, euphorbia herb, gentian
 root, goldenseal root, grindelia robusta
 herb, nux vomica (the principles will be
 reported) passion flower herb, quassia
 chips, rhatany root, sandalwood chips,
 senega root, serpentaria root and pine
 and cherry bark (to be replaced with their
 extracts).
 Natural materials continue to be re-

the cost of gathering and processing some
 items has become prohibitive in view of
 their limited use.

Agar—Sellers report USP Kobe Num-
 ber 1 strip agar at \$2.90 and \$3.25. The
 quote varies with the seller.
 They report powdered material at \$2.48
 and \$2.70 a pound.

Rhubarb Root—A check of botanicals
 suppliers last week found that the high
 quote for powdered rhubarb had climbed
 since a check made in March, when the
 highest quote as 64c. a pound.

The highest quote last week was 73c.
 a pound. The lowest quote was 61c. a
 pound.

Senna Leaves—During the same period,
 the quote for Number 3 Tinevelly senna
 leaves climbed 3c. a pound to 26c. a
 pound.

The sole obtainable quote for powdered
 Tinevelly leaves dropped 3c. a pound to
 40c. Tinevelly pods and Tinevelly leaves
 No. 1 and 2 were unchanged.

The No. 1 leaves are priced at 35c. a
 pound, the No. 2 at 31c. and the pods at
 35c. Alexandrian leaf prices are also un-
 changed at 43c. a pound for whole ma-
 terial.

Uva-Ursi—A check of uva-ursi leaf
 prices failed to turn up any quotes last
 week. The last quotes obtained in similar
 checks put the price range at 20c. to 25c.
 a pound.

Energy vs. Pollution Control

Continued from Page 5
 developed, there will be a loss of 44,500
 coal mining jobs, "including 15,000 in
 my own state of West Virginia."
 Dr. Ralph E. Lapp, of Quadri-Science,
 Inc., told the hearing that the motor car
 industry accounts for 95 percent of the
 prime-mover horsepower in the US.

sources, which has been advocated by
 the White House.
 Such an agency would consolidate the
 authority necessary to implement the
 national energy policy toward which the
 Administration and Congress are working,
 Mr. Morton explained.
 He urged development of an "energy
 ethic" which would make the best uses

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